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2 ***Spiribacter roseus* sp. nov., a new moderately halophilic species of the genus**3 ***Spiribacter* from salterns**

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12 Running title: *Spiribacter roseus* sp. nov.

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22 The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession number for the 16S rRNA gene sequence of

23 *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T is LT578364.

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25 Four pink-pigmented, non-motile, Gram-staining-negative and moderately
26 halophilic curved rods, designated strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4, were
27 isolated from a saltern located in Isla Cristina, Huelva, South West Spain.
28 Phylogenetic analyses based on 16S rRNA gene sequences showed that they were
29 members of the genus *Spiribacter*, most closely related to *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-
30 SP71^T (99.3-99.5 % sequence similarity) and *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T (96.5-
31 96.7 %). Other related species were *Alkalilimnicola ehrlichii* MLHE-1^T (95.1-
32 95.3 %), *Arhodomonas recens* RS91^T (95.1-95.2 %) and *Arhodomonas aquaeolei*
33 ATCC 49307^T (95.0-95.1 %), all members of the family *Ectothiorhodospiraceae*. The
34 major fatty acids were C_{18:1} ω_{6c} and/or C_{18:1} ω_{7c}, C_{16:0}, and C_{12:0}. The DNA G+C
35 range was 64.0-66.3 mol%. The DNA-DNA hybridization between strains SSL50^T,
36 SSL25, SSL97, SSL4, and *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T were 37-49 %. The
37 average nucleotide identity (ANI_b) values between the strain SSL50^T genome and
38 the two other *Spiribacter* species, *S. curvatus* UAH-SP71^T and *S. salinus* M19-40^T
39 were 82.4 % and 79.1 %, respectively, supporting the proposal of a new species of
40 the genus *Spiribacter*. On the basis of the polyphasic analysis, the four new isolates
41 are considered to represent a novel species of *Spiribacter*, for which the name
42 *Spiribacter roseus* sp. nov. is proposed. The type strain is SSL50^T (= CECT 9117^T =
43 IBRC-M 11076^T).

44

45 Hypersaline environments are extreme habitats in which the main life limiting factor is
46 their high salt concentration. In this regard, multi-pond solar salterns constitute excellent
47 models for studies focused on the microbial diversity and ecology over a wide range of
48 salt concentrations. The microbial community of crystallizer ponds has been extensively
49 studied and their most abundant archaeal and bacterial inhabitants have been obtained in
50 pure culture, whereas intermediate salinity ponds have received much less attention
51 (Ventosa *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, studies using culture-independent techniques for the
52 analysis of the microbial diversity dwelling in intermediate salinity saltern ponds have
53 shown that the most abundant microbes have not been retrieved in axenic cultures yet,
54 possibly due to their slow growing time and particular requirement of nutrients being very
55 different to the ones commonly used in laboratories studies (Ghai *et al.*, 2011; Fernández
56 *et al.*, 2014a; 2014b). As a consequence, culture-based studies conducted on these habitats
57 have led to the isolation of microorganisms detected in negligible abundance by culture-
58 independent techniques, which provide a more realistic view of their diversity. This
59 prevents scientific community from studying and understanding the primary relationships
60 and functions of microbes in these natural environments.

61 Recently, León *et al.* (2014) described the genus *Spiribacter*, an abundant moderate
62 halophile thriving in intermediate salinity saltern ponds as ascertained by metagenomic
63 assemblies and recruitment analysis. It belongs to the family *Ectothiorhodospiraceae*,
64 within the order *Chromatiales*, class *Gammaproteobacteria* in the phylum
65 *Proteobacteria*. To date, this genus includes two species isolated from salterns,
66 *Spiribacter salinus* (León *et al.* 2014; Oren and Garrity, 2014) and *Spiribacter curvatus*
67 (León *et al.* 2015), which genomes were sequenced and assembled into a single contig
68 (López-Pérez *et al.*, 2013). *Spiribacter* cells are characterized by a peculiar morphology,

69 adopting short and thin curved rods morphology on young cultures and spiral shapes at
70 the stationary phase.

71 Metagenomic studies carried out from concentrator saltern ponds with 19 % and 21 %
72 NaCl located in Santa Pola (East coast of Spain) and Isla Cristina (Southwest of Spain),
73 respectively, showed that a high number of the metagenomics contigs assembled
74 belonged to *Spiribacter* (Fernández *et al.* 2014b; León *et al.*, 2014), which indicates that
75 this genus is very abundant in these environment. However, a closer look at these contigs
76 revealed that some of them had low similarity to *S. salinus* and *S. curvatus* genomes,
77 while still being syntenic to them. This suggested that there may be other very abundant
78 species in these environments. On the basis of these data, four strains closely related to
79 *Spiribacter*, were obtained from the water of ponds of Isla Cristina saltern in Spain. In
80 this study we combine a genomic analysis as well as a polyphasic approach with the aim
81 of defining the taxonomic position of these new strains. Based on the obtained data we
82 propose the placement of the four strains as a new species within the genus *Spiribacter*,
83 for which we propose the name *Spiribacter roseus* sp. nov.

84

85 Taking into consideration the culture conditions already used for the cultivation of the
86 previously described species of *Spiribacter*, the growth characteristics and the peculiar
87 morphology adopted by the cells of this genus, we carried out a sampling aimed to
88 exclusively obtain other bacterial strains phylogenetically related to the genus
89 *Spiribacter*. Four strains, SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4, were isolated from water
90 samples from a pond of a marine saltern located in Isla Cristina, Huelva, South West
91 Spain. Samples were collected in sterile containers and transported within 4-5 h of its
92 collection to the laboratory and plated on a modified SM medium, previously described
93 by León *et al.* (2014), designated as SMM medium. The composition of the SMM

94 medium was (g l^{-1}): NaCl, 46.8; $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 19.5; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 30.5; CaCl_2 , 0.5; KCl,
95 3.0; NaHCO_3 , 0.1; NaBr, 0.35; casein digest, 5.0 and sodium pyruvate, 1.1. The pH was
96 adjusted to 7.5 with KOH 4 M. Strains were routinely grown in this medium at 37 °C for
97 10 days. These cultures were maintained at -80 °C in SMM medium containing 50 % (v/v)
98 glycerol. The type strains *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T and *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-
99 SP71^T were used as reference strains for comparative purposes. They were cultivated
100 under the same conditions as the four new isolates.

101

102 For the determination of the cellular morphology and motility, cultures grown on SMM
103 medium were examined under a phase-contrast microscope (Olympus CX41). Cellular
104 morphology was also examined by electron microscopy after growth on SMM medium
105 at 37 °C on a shaking incubator at 200 rpm until they reached the exponential-stationary
106 phase. The cells were then collected by centrifugation and fixed in 1.6 % glutaraldehyde
107 buffered with 0.1 M cacodilate (pH 7.4) for one hour at room temperature and 24 hours
108 at 4 °C. They were then postfixed in a 1 % (w/v) osmium tetroxide solution for one hour
109 at 4 °C. The dehydration was performed in an increasing series of acetone (50-100 %) and
110 the samples were embedded in Spurr resin and stained with 2 % (w/v) aqueous uranyl
111 acetate for 2 hours. Blocks were obtained by polymerization at 70 °C for 8 hours. After
112 hardening, ultrathin sections were cut with a diamond knife and then counterstained with
113 uranyl acetate and lead citrate using an automatic counterstaining machine (Leica AC20).
114 The thin sections were observed using a Zeiss Libra 120 at the CITIUS Center of the
115 University of Sevilla, Spain. As previously reported for species of *Spiribacter*, the cells
116 of strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4 have small sizes, forming thin curved rods
117 on young cultures and spirals at the late exponential and stationary phase. These spiral
118 cells are not as long as those reported for *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T. At the beginning

119 of the exponential phase, the cells look like curved rods-nearly closed rings-with a size
120 of 0.2-0.3 μm wide by 1.6-1.8 μm long (Fig 1). When they reach the late exponential
121 phase cells have spiral shapes, 2.0-3.0 μm long. Polyalkanoate inclusion bodies are
122 observed. By both, optical and electron microscopy, we also observe round structures,
123 with a prolongation in many cases, along all the growth phases. These structures were
124 also present in *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T (León *et al.*, 2014), but they are more evident
125 in the four new isolates.

126

127 The morphology of colonies, their size and pigmentation were observed on SMM solid
128 medium after 10 days of incubation at 37 °C. Optimal conditions for growth were
129 determined by growing the strains in SMM liquid medium adjusted to 0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8,
130 1.0, 1.3, 1.6, 1.8, 2.0 and 2.2 M NaCl, and at temperatures of 15, 20, 28, 30, 37, 40 and
131 45 °C, respectively. Growth rates were determined by monitoring the increase in the
132 optical density at 600 nm. The pH range for the isolates was tested in SMM medium
133 adjusted to pH 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 7.5, 8.0, 9.0 and 10.0 with the addition of the appropriate
134 buffering capacity to each medium (Sánchez-Porro *et al.*, 2009). All biochemical tests
135 were carried out in SMM medium at 37 °C, unless otherwise stated. Growth under
136 anaerobic conditions (with H₂/CO₂) was determined by incubating strains in an anaerobic
137 chamber in SMM solid medium. Catalase activity was determined by adding a 1 % (w/v)
138 H₂O₂ solution to colonies on SMM agar medium. Oxidase test was performed using the
139 Dry Slide Assay (Difco). The following tests were determined as described by Cowan &
140 Steel (1965) growing the cells on SMM medium: hydrolysis of aesculin, casein, gelatin,
141 starch or Tween 80, Voges-Proskauer and methyl red tests, production of indole,
142 phosphatase, urease, nitrate and nitrite reduction. Citrate utilization was determined on
143 Simon's citrate medium supplemented with 10 % (w/v) salts. For determining the range

144 of substrates used as carbon and energy sources or as carbon, nitrogen and energy sources,
145 the classical medium of Koser (1923) as modified by Ventosa *et al.* (1982) was used.
146 Substrates were added as filter-sterilized solutions to give a final concentration of 1 g l⁻¹,
147 except for carbohydrates, which were used at 2 g l⁻¹.

148 Cells of the new isolates were Gram-stain-negative, non-motile, and strictly aerobic. The
149 four strains showed catalase and oxidase activities. They were moderately halophilic
150 bacteria, able to grow in SMM medium with 8 to 20 % total salts, with optimal growth at
151 10 % salts; they were not able to grow in the absence of NaCl. The cells were able to
152 grow from 15 to 40 °C, being the optimal growth at 37 °C. The pH range for growth was
153 7-9 with the optimal growth at pH 7.5-8.0. Urease and phosphatase were positive for all
154 strains (in the species *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T urease was negative, but
155 phosphatase was positive). Nitrate and nitrite were not reduced. Hydrolysis of aesculin,
156 starch, casein, gelatine and Tween 80 were negative. The available genomic sequence of
157 the type strain SSL50^T has been of considerable importance in the phenotypic
158 characterization of this new bacterium because it has allowed us to contrast the
159 experimental data obtained in the laboratory with those obtained from the genomic
160 analysis. The analysis of the complete genome of the strain SSL50^T showed a simplified
161 metabolic versatility for this bacterium, as occurs with the other two *Spiribacter* species.
162 Strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4 had very reduced ability to utilize organic
163 compounds as sole carbon and energy sources (Table 1).

164

165 Genomic DNA from strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4 was prepared using the G-
166 spinTM Total extraction kit (Intron Biotechnology) according to the manufacturer's
167 instructions. The 16S rRNA gene sequences of strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4
168 were obtained from the complete genome sequence. The almost-complete 16S rRNA

169 gene sequence of strains SSL50^T (1548 bp), SSL25 (1548 bp), SSL97 (1549 bp) and SSL4
170 (1548 bp) were obtained, deposited in GenBank, and used for initial BLAST searches in
171 GenBank and for phylogenetic analysis. The identification of phylogenetic neighbours
172 and the calculation of pairwise 16S rRNA gene sequence similarities were achieved using
173 the EzTaxon-e tool (Kim *et al.*, 2012). The 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis showed
174 that strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4 were members of the genus *Spiribacter*.
175 The 16S rRNA gene sequence similarities between strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and
176 SSL4 were 99.9 % and between these four strains and the most closely related species of
177 *Spiribacter*, *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T were 99.3 %, 99.3 %, 99.5 % and 99.4 %,
178 respectively, and with *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T were 96.5 %, 96.5 %, 96.7 % and
179 96.5 % sequence similarities, respectively. Other related species were *Alkalilimnicola*
180 *ehrichii* MLHE-1^T (95.1-95.3 %), *Arhodomonas recens* RS91^T (95.1-95.2 %) and
181 *Arhodomonas aquaeolei* ATCC 49307^T (95.0-95.1 %), all members of the family
182 *Ectothiorhodospiraceae*. Those high similarity values might indicate that the new strains
183 could constitute novel strains of the species *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T within the
184 genus *Spiribacter*. However, some significant differences in the cultures of these new
185 strains, such as their growth rates, colonies pigmentation and the optical density reached,
186 with respect to the species *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T were noticed and led us to
187 further investigate their taxonomic affiliation.

188 The 16S rRNA gene sequences were aligned with the published sequences from closely
189 related bacteria and the alignments were confirmed and checked against both primary and
190 secondary structures of the 16S rRNA molecule using the alignment tool of the ARB
191 software package version 5.5 (Ludwig *et al.*, 2004). Phylogenetic trees were constructed
192 using three different methods: maximum-parsimony (Fitch, 1971), neighbour-joining
193 (Saitou & Nei, 1987) and maximum-likelihood (Felsenstein, 1981) algorithms integrated

194 in the ARB software for phylogenetic inference. Bootstrap analysis was based on 1000
195 resamplings (Felsenstein, 1985). The 16S rRNA gene sequences used for phylogenetic
196 comparisons were obtained from the GenBank database and their strain designations and
197 accession numbers are shown in Fig 2. The 16S rRNA-based phylogenetic tree
198 constructed using the maximum-parsimony algorithm revealed that strains SSL50^T,
199 SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4 clustered with the two *Spiribacter* species, being most closely
200 related to the species *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T. The topology obtained using the
201 maximum-parsimony algorithm was also observed in the trees generated using the
202 neighbour-joining and maximum-likelihood methods. Despite the close relation between
203 the four new isolates and the species *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T, we continued our
204 studies with the aim to determine if these new strains could constitute a new species.
205 While a 97 % 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity has been the traditionally accepted cut-
206 off value for species delineation it has been shown that strains with similarities higher
207 than 97 % could still constitute different taxa.

208

209 The G+C content of the genomic DNA of strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4 was
210 determined from the mid-point value (T_m) of the thermal denaturation profile (Marmur
211 and Doty, 1962) using the equation of Owen & Hill (1979), obtained with a Perkin-Elmer
212 UV-Vis Lambda 20 spectrophotometer at 260 nm equipped with a PTP-1 peltier system
213 programmed with an increasing of temperature of 1 °C/min. These values were also
214 calculated from the complete genome sequences. The DNA G+C content of strains
215 SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4 were estimated to be 64.2, 66.3, 64.0 and 64.0 mol%,
216 respectively. These values are within the range reported for the family
217 *Ectothiorhodospiraceae* (50.5 to 69.9 mol%) (Imhoff, 1984) and very close to the values

218 reported for the species of the genus *Spiribacter*: 62.7 % for *S. salinus* M19-40^T (León *et*
219 *al.*, 2014) and 63.9 % for *S. curvatus* UAH-SP71^T (León *et al.*, 2015) (Table 1).

220

221 In order to determine if the four new isolates constituted a new species or if they could
222 be assigned to the species *Spiribacter curvatus*, we carried out DNA-DNA hybridization
223 studies between the four strains and the type strains of the most closely related species,
224 *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T. DNA-DNA hybridization studies were performed by
225 the competition procedure of the membrane filter method (Johnson, 1994). The
226 hybridization temperature was 54.6 °C, which is within the limit of validity for the filter
227 method (De Ley & Tijtgat, 1970) and the percentage of hybridization was calculated
228 according to Johnson (1994). The experiments were performed in triplicate. The
229 percentages of DNA-DNA hybridization (DDH) between strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97,
230 SSL4, and *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T were 42 %, 38 %, 49 % and 37 %,
231 respectively. These DDH relatedness values were lower than 70 % threshold, currently
232 accepted as the cut-off value for species delineation (Stackebrandt *et al.*, 1994; 2002),
233 and indicate that the new strains constitute a genotypically distinct taxon.

234

235 In order to elucidate if the strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4 might belong to a
236 single clonal line a fingerprinting study based on BOX-PCR was carried out. PCRs were
237 carried out in a total volume of 50 µl including 50 ng/µl genomic DNA, 10X reaction
238 buffer, 25 mM MgCl₂, 1.25 mM each dNTP, 12 µM each primer and 5 U/µl *Taq* DNA
239 polymerase. BOX-PCRs were performed with primer BOXA1R (5'-
240 CTACGGCAAGGCGACGCTGACG-3') (Versalovic *et al.*, 1994). PCR conditions were
241 as follows: 95 °C for 3 min followed by 30 cycles of 94 °C for 30 s, 53 °C for 1 min and
242 70 °C for 8 min (BOX-PCR) and finally 70 °C for 16 min. PCR products were separated

243 by electrophoresis on 1.5 % agarose gels in 1 X TAE buffer for 2.5 h at 50 V, stained
244 with ethidium bromide. The obtained data showed that the new isolates were not clonal
245 strains, since clear differences on the banding pattern were observed (Supplementary Fig.
246 S1).

247

248 The availability of the complete genome of strain SSL50^T and of the most closely related
249 species permitted us to calculate the average nucleotide identity (ANIb) (Konstantinidis
250 and Tiedje, 2005), which is a key feature for the precise delineation of this new species,
251 considering the high sequence similarity of the 16S rRNA gene of this strain with *S.*
252 *curvatus* UAH-SP71^T (99.3%). The average nucleotide identity (ANI) values between the
253 strain SSL50^T genome and the two other *Spiribacter* species, *S. curvatus* UAH-SP71^T
254 and *S. salinus* M19-40^T were 82.4 % and 79.1 %, respectively, as expected for different
255 species of the same genus. These values are lower than 94 %, generally accepted as
256 threshold percentage for species delineation (Konstantinidis and Tiedje, 2005), and
257 support the proposal of a new species.

258

259 Fatty acids analysis was performed using the MIDI Microbial Identification System
260 (MIDI, 2008). Cells of the type strain SSL50^T were cultured on SM15 agar medium at 37
261 °C for 10 days, the same conditions used by León *et al.* (2014; 2015) for the previously
262 described *Spiribacter* species. The extraction and analysis of fatty acids were performed
263 according to the recommendations of the MIDI system. This analysis was carried out by
264 the CECT (Spanish Collection of Type Cultures, Valencia, Spain) using gas
265 chromatography (Agilent 6850) and a standardized protocol according to the MIDI
266 Sherlock system (Sasser, 1990). The cellular fatty acids profile of strain SSL50^T was
267 characterized by the fatty acids C_{18:1} ω6c and/or C_{18:1} ω7c (summed feature 8; 50.0 %),

268 C_{16:0} (28.3 %), and C_{12:0} (6.7 %) as the major fatty acids, and minor amounts of C_{19:0} cyclo
269 *ω*8c (3.9 %), C_{10:0} 3-OH (3.3 %), C_{12:0} 3-OH (3.1 %) and C_{19:1} *ω*6c and/or C_{19:0} cyclo *ω*10c
270 (summed feature 7; 3.0 %) were present. This fatty acids profile is quite similar to those
271 reported for the species of the genus *Spiribacter* (Table 2). However, different proportions
272 in the predominant fatty acids were observed in strain SSL50^T compared to *Spiribacter*
273 *salinus* M19-40^T and *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T. Besides, the fatty acids C_{14:0}
274 3OH, iso-C_{16:1} and/or C_{12:0} aldehyde are absent in SSL50^T but not in the most closely
275 related species *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T (summed feature 2; 2.0 %).

276

277 The results obtained from this polyphasic taxonomic study based on phylogenetic,
278 genotypic, chemotaxonomic and phenotypic studies and the data reported from the
279 comparative genomic study supports the delineation of a new species within the genus
280 *Spiribacter*, for which we propose the name *Spiribacter roseus* sp. nov.

281

282 **Description of *Spiribacter roseus* sp. nov.**

283 *Spiribacter roseus* (ro'se.us. L. adj. *roseus* pink pigmented).

284

285 Cells are Gram-stain-negative, non-endospore forming and non-motile. When the cells
286 are grown on SMM medium they adopt a curved rod morphology in young cultures (0.2-
287 0.3 x 1.6-1.8 μm) and short spiral shape in the late exponential and stationary phase.
288 Colonies on SMM medium are circular, pink-pigmented and 0.5-1.0 mm in diameter after
289 10 days of incubation at 37 °C. Moderately halophilic. Growth occurs in SMM medium
290 with 8 to 20 % (w/v) total salts, at pH 7-9 and at 15-40 °C, with optimal growth at 10 %
291 (w/v) salts, pH 7.5-8.0 and 37 °C. Strictly aerobic. Catalase and oxidase positive.
292 Hydrolysis of aesculin, casein, gelatin, starch and Tween 80 are negative. Urease positive

293 and phosphatase weakly positive. Nitrate and nitrite are not reduced. Indole is not
294 produced. Simmons' citrate is negative. Pyruvate and glycerol are used as carbon and
295 energy sources. The following compounds are not utilized as sole carbon and energy
296 sources: D-arabinose, D-glucose, lactose, D-mannose, raffinose, ribose, L-alanine, L-
297 glutamine, L-methionine, DL-phenylalanine, D-mannitol, D-sorbitol, xylitol, citrate,
298 fumarate, propionate and DL-tartrate. The major fatty acids are C_{18:1 ω6c} and/or C_{18:1 ω7c},
299 C_{16:0}, and C_{12:0}. The DNA G+C range is 64.0-66.3 mol% (Tm).
300 The type strain is SSL50^T (= CECT 9117^T = IBRC-M 11076^T), isolated from the water of
301 a pond of Isla Cristina saltern, Huelva (Spain). The DNA G+C content of the type strain
302 is 64.2 mol% (determined by the Tm method) and 66.0 % (calculated from the genome
303 sequence).

304

305

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312

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402

403 **Legend to figures**

404

405 **Fig. 1.** Maximum-parsimony phylogenetic tree based on the complete 16S rRNA gene
406 sequences showing the relationships between strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97, SSL4 and
407 the most closely related species of the genus *Spiribacter* and other members of the family
408 *Ectothiorhodospiraceae*. Sequence accession numbers used are shown in parentheses.
409 Bootstrap values higher than 70 % are indicated at branch-points. *Thermus thermophilus*
410 HB8^T (GenBank accession no. X07998) was used as an outgroup. The
411 GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession number of each sequence is shown in parentheses. Bar,
412 0.01 nucleotide changes per position.

413

414 **Fig. 2.** Transmission electron microphotographs (A-D) of thin sections of cells of
415 *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T grown on SMM liquid medium at late exponential phase. Bars,
416 0.2 μm (A), 1 μm (B); 1 μm (C); 0.5 μm (D).

417

418 **Table 1.** Differential characteristics of strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97, SSL4 and the type
 419 strain of the two closely related species of the genus *Spiribacter*.
 420 Strains: 1, SSL50^T; 2, SSL25; 3, SSL97; 4, SSL4; 5, *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T;
 421 6, *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T.
 422 +, Positive; -, negative.

Characteristic	1	2	3	4	5	6
Cell morphology	Curved rods-nearly closed rings, short spiral cells	Thin curved rods, some spiral cells	Thin curved rods, long spiral cells			
Colony pigmentation	Pink	Pale pink	Pale pink	Pink	Dark pink	Pink
Cell size (µm)	0.2-0.3 x 1.6-1.8	0.2-0.3 x 1.6-1.8	0.2-0.3 x 1.6-1.8	0.2-0.3 x 1.6-1.8	0.5-1.5	0.3 x 0.8-1.8
NaCl range (M)	0.8-2.2	0.6-2.2	0.6-2.2	0.6-2.2	0.8-3.4	0.6-2.4
NaCl optimum (M)	0.8-1.0	1.3-1.6	1.0-1.3	1.3-1.6	1.7	0.8-1.0
Temperature range for growth (°C)	15-40	15-40	15-40	15-40	5-40	15-40
pH range	7.0-9.0	7.0-9.0	7.0-9.0	7.0-9.0	5.0-10.0	6.0-9.0
pH optimum	7.5-8.0	7.5-8.0	7.5-8.0	7.5-8.0	8.0	7.5-8.0
Urease	+	+	+	+	-	+
Phosphatase	+	+	+	+	+	-
DNA G+C content (%)	64.2 ^a (66.0 ^b)	66.3 ^a	64.0 ^a	64.0 ^a	60.4 (63.9) ^c	60.0 (62.7) ^c

423

424 ^a Data from the T_m method; ^b data from the genome sequence; ^c data (T_m and genome
 425 sequence, respectively) from León *et al.* (2015).

426

427 **Table 2.** Cellular fatty acids composition of strain SSL50^T and the most closely related
 428 species of the genus *Spiribacter*. All data were obtained under the same growth
 429 conditions. Values are percentages of the total cellular fatty acids. Strains: 1, strain
 430 SSL50^T; 2, *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T (León *et al.*, 2014) and 3, *Spiribacter curvatus*
 431 UAH-SP71^T (León *et al.*, 2015). Values lower than 0.5 % are not shown. -, Not detected.
 432

Fatty acid	1	2	3
C _{9:0}	-	0.6	-
C _{10:0}	0.7	0.6	1.2
C _{10:0} 3-OH	3.3	4.0	6.4
C _{12:0}	6.7	3.5	5.7
C _{12:0} 3-OH	3.1	1.3	1.2
C _{14:1} ω5c	-	0.8	-
Summed feature 2*	-	-	2.0
Summed feature 3*	2.5	8.6	3.6
C _{14:0}	0.6	0.8	0.8
C _{16:0}	28.3	9.3	13.4
Summed feature 8*	50.0	60.6	60.6
C _{17:0}	-	1.8	-
C _{17:1} ω8c	-	2.1	-
C _{17:1} ω6c	-	1.0	-
C _{18:0}	2.1	1.2	1.6
C _{18:1} ω9c	0.8	-	-
Summed feature 7*	3.0	1.9	0.6
C _{19:0} cyclo ω8c	3.9	1.0	2.2

433 * Summed features are groups of two or three fatty acids that could not be separated by
 434 GC with the MIDI system. Summed feature 2 comprised C_{14:0} 3OH, iso-C_{16:1} and/or C_{12:0}
 435 aldehyde, summed feature 3 comprised C_{16:1} ω6c and/or C_{16:1} ω7c, summed feature 7

436 comprised $C_{19:1} \omega 6c$ and/or $C_{19:0}$ cyclo $\omega 10c$ and summed feature 8 comprised $C_{18:1} \omega 6c$
437 and/or $C_{18:1} \omega 7c$.

438

0.01

***Spiribacter roseus* sp. nov., a new moderately halophilic species of the genus**

***Spiribacter* from salterns**

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Suppl. Fig. S1. Genotypic fingerprint patterns of strains SSL50^T, SSL25, SSL97 and SSL4 obtained with BOX-PCR. Strains: 1, SSL50^T; 2, SSL25; 3, SSL97; 4, SSL4; 5, *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T and 6, *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T. M, 1 kb DNA ladder.

